

**A STUDY OF ICT INFRASTRUCTURE AVAILABLE IN THE COLLEGES AND
INSTITUTES AFFILIATED TO NORTH MAHARASHTRA
UNIVERSITY, JALGAON**

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Abstract:-

The ICT becomes a pathway of acquainting the knowledge. During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. "Internet availability" with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose 50% Office Heads rated as Average. The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – "Wi-Fi Internet connectivity" with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose Majority 48% Office Heads rated as Average. The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – "Internet speed" with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose Majority 46.1% Office Heads rated as Average. "Availability of Separate office server" with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose majority 45.1% Office Heads rated as Average. Local Networking" with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose Majority 48% Office Heads rated as Average.

Key words- *Wi-Fi Internet, ICT, Administration, etc.*

Introduction:-

ICT enabled education is a need of time. In 21st century we are witnessing the fourth Information Revolution in Education sector- The ICT Revolution. Now a days the whole world is shrunked in to a small village. The ICT becomes a pathway of acquainting the knowledge. Every Higher Education must have advanced ICT infrastructure. It's a duty of every college an Institutes administration to provide an adequate ICT facilities, so that the Teachers can shape the students towards smart citizens. This study aims to identify the ICT infrastructure available for Teachers of Colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon.

Material and Method :-

During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. Primary data is collected from various Teachers associated with colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University with the help of structured questionnaire. The research practices are comprise of random sampling, data collection, data editing, data classification, tabulation and interpretation of data with the help of statistical tools.

Observation -

Table 1: Internet availability

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Internet availability	Very Good	16	15.7
	Good	25	24.5
	Average	51	50
	Poor	10	9.8

Figure 1 :- Internet availability

Table 2: Wi-Fi Internet connectivity

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Wi-Fi Internet connectivity	Very Good	14	13.7
	Good	25	24.5
	Average	49	48
	Poor	12	11.8
	Very Poor	2	2

Figure 2 :- Wi-Fi Internet connectivity

Table3: Internet speed

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Internet speed	Very Good	16	15.7
	Good	29	28.4
	Average	47	46.1
	Poor	10	9.8

Figure 3 :- Internet speed

Table 4: Availability of Separate office server

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Availability of Separate office server	Very Good	8	7.8
	Good	34	33.3
	Average	46	45.1
	Poor	10	9.8
	Very Poor	4	3.9

Figure 4: Availability of Separate office server

Table 5: Local Networking

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Local Networking	Very Good	18	17.6
	Good	23	22.5
	Average	49	48
	Poor	12	11.8

Figure 5: Local Networking

Result and Discussion:-

The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – “Internet availability” with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose. 15.7% Office Heads rated as Very Good, 24.5% Office Heads rated as Good, Majority 50% Office Heads rated as Average and 9.8% Office Heads rated as Poor

The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – “Wi-Fi Internet connectivity” with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose. 13.7% Office Heads rated as Very Good, 24.5% Office Heads rated as Good, Majority 48% Office Heads rated as Average, 11.8% Office Heads rated as Poor and 2% Office Heads rated as Very Poor.

The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – “Internet speed” with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose. 15.7% Office Heads rated as Very Good, 28.4% Office Heads rated as Good, Majority 46.1% Office Heads rated as Average and 9.8% Office Heads rated as Poor.

The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – “Availability of Separate office server” with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose. 7.8% Office Heads rated as Very Good, 33.3% Office Heads rated as Good, Majority 45.1% Office Heads rated as Average, 9.8% Office Heads rated as Poor and 3.9% Office Heads rated as Very Poor.

The Office Heads when they requested to rate-readiness parameter – “Local Networking” with respect to Computer usage in their college for academic and administrative purpose. 17.6% Office Heads rated as Very Good, 22.5% Office Heads rated as Good, Majority 48% Office Heads rated as Average and 11.8% Office Heads rated as Poor.

References:-

1. *E-Service Quality Management*. **Lorena Batagan, Aadrian Pocovnicu, Sergiu Capisizu**. s.l. : 4, 2009, Journal of Applied Quantitative Techniques, Vol. 3.
2. *Managing Rural Citizen Interfaces in e-Governance Systems: A Study in Indian Context*. **Misra, Harekrishna**. Bogota, Colombia : ACM, 2009. ICEGOV2009.
3. *Factors for Successful e-Government Adoption: a Conceptual Framework*. **Vinod Kumar, Bhasker Mukerji, Irfan Butt, Ajax Persaud**. 1, 2007, The Electronic Journal of e-Government, Vol. 5, pp. 63 - 76.